

REPRESENTATION OF CULTURAL VALUES IN THE MEDIA LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

The article deals with the study of the concept of culture in understanding the cognitive aspects of mass media text and the denotative English cultural context.

Along with the picture of the world and ideology, the concept of culture is essential for understanding the cognitive aspect of mass media texts. A look at mass media texts through the prism of the modern concept of culture allows us not only to understand their role in the cultural context of the "information society", but also to identify those significant characteristics from the point of view of cultural studies that are inherent in various types of media texts. Like ideology, culture refers to complex multilevel concepts, the interpretation of which is conditioned both by the framework of a particular scientific approach and by the specific context of a certain discourse, for example, speech culture, culture agriculture, the culture of ancient Greece, mass culture, youth culture, etc. The need for a theoretical understanding of the problems identified in this area, as well as the urgency of developing methods for describing culturally significant components of speech led to the formation of a new section of the science of language - linguoculturology.

Linguoculturology emerged as a synthesizing type of discipline based on the achievements of ethno-, psycho-, and sociolinguistics, on the traditions of linguistic and cultural studies. Linguoculturology as a separate discipline is presented most fully in the book by V.V.Vorobyov "Linguoculturology. To study the cultural layer of mass media texts, the idea that the text is a verbal and symbolic symbolization of culture is extremely important. Understanding that the text is densely saturated with culturally significant information allows us to consider it as a voluminous multidimensional phenomenon that unfolds not only in the verbal linear plane, but is characterized by depth and multilevel structure. To denote the totality of culturally significant information present in the text both in an open explicit form and expressed implicitly, most often the word "context" is used in various terminological combinations, for example, socio-cultural context, extralinguistic context, and vertical context.

Within the framework of media linguistics, the term “cultural context” is used. The preference for the word “culturological” rather than “cultural” is because the adjective “cultural” in combination with the concept of context is perceived rather as “relevant to a particular culture”, while the combination with the adjective “culturological” emphasizes the formality of culture-specific knowledge. Thus, the cultural context can be defined as a level-structured set of all culturally relevant information contained in the text. The concept of cultural context involves the allocation of the following levels:

- 1) denotative, when culturally significant information is expressed in a direct explicit form;
- 2) connotative, in which culture-specific information is contained in expressive-emotional-evaluative connotations;
- 3) associative, when culture-specific components are represented in associative connections of lexical and phraseological units, and metaphorical, which combines culture-specific information reflected in metaphors, comparisons, and images are inherent in a particular language collective[1, 200].

The denotative cultural context is represented by words and phrases denoting the realities peculiar to a particular culture. These can be proper names, for example, names of famous people, names of political parties, streets, historical places, architectural monuments, etc., as well as words denoting a particular culturally specific phenomenon or artifact, for example, backbencher, fish-and-chips, kilt, car-boot sale. Saturation with culture-specific units of this kind is an essential feature of mass media texts, which, due to their reflectivity, directly correlate with the events of current life. A story about what is happening in the country and abroad, analysis, commentary, coverage of events in the materials of the features group, advertising - all this naturally “grows” on a certain cultural soil, reflecting the realities and specific facts from the life of a particular language collective. All four types of English considered in this paper media texts contain a significant number of words and phrases denoting the realities of English reality. At the same time, understanding some culture-specific units does not cause many difficulties, since they are often found in international news, telling about events in the UK. We are talking about the names of political parties, the names of current politicians, the main symbols of political power, and other realities of English political life. For example, such realities as Tories and Labor, Westminster, 10 Downing Street, and IRA, are known to many. Understanding other culture-specific units, the use of which is limited to English media texts proper and does not apply to international news, requires a deeper knowledge of English reality. So, texts containing such culture-specific units as a backbencher, frontbench spokesman, Shadow minister, Privy Purse, Plaid Cymru, etc. can only be adequately understood if there is appropriate background knowledge. For example, understanding the following fragments require an appropriate understanding of the structure and distribution of places in The British Parliament.

“With these opinions, he was not in line with the policies of the Cabinet and has been on the backbenches for a good many years.

Prime Minister didn't happen to be in the House when he made this speech, but Mr. Biffen did add with due humility, as he's now a backbencher, that he hoped this would be brought to the Prime Minister's notice”.

The word backbencher means an ordinary member of the British Parliament, a “backbencher” since the backbenches in the British House of Commons are intended for ordinary members, and the front ones, respectively, for members of the government and leading figures of the “shadow cabinet” (shadow cabinet), or the opposition.

“Backbenchers are Members of Parliament (MPs) who are not government or opposition ministers. ‘Bench’ is the name for a long seat on which several people sit, and MPs who are not in government sit at the back of the House of Commons” [Nation M, 1991, 6].

These explanations allow us to fully reveal the meaning of the above passages, in particular, to understand why “being not in line with the policies of the government involves sitting on the backbenches, which, in turn, forces us to speak “with due humility”. Speaking about the culture-specific units of the denotative level, it should also be noted that when they get into the sphere of the international media flow, they are immediately provided with appropriate explanations intended for a wide international audience. For example, a well-known Irish organization in the British Isles Sinn Fein is represented in the article of the newspaper “The Moscow Times” as “IRA's political wing” - the political wing of the Irish Republican Army:

“On Saturday, Protestant unionist leader David Trimble rejected a new Irish Republican Army offer on weapons disarmament as too vague, and Gerry Adams, president of the IRA’s political wing, Sinn Fein, accused the British government of betraying the 1998 Good Friday agreement to save Trimble”.

It should also be noted that in the field of mass communication, the metaphorical context is extremely mobile and is constantly “fueled” by the media texts themselves: a successful phrase, a memorable utterance instantly spreads throughout the information space, repeating in different versions in one or another text. Some text fragments are quoted unexpectedly often, appearing simultaneously in several media materials at once, which gives the impression of a complex chain of borrowings, which is almost impossible to track. And if understanding the denotative context is enough information of a historical and socio-cultural nature contained in linguistic and cultural dictionaries, then an adequate understanding of the metaphorical context requires special background knowledge, namely knowledge of texts that are the most important component of national culture.

References:

1. Добросклонская, Т. Г. Медиалингвистика: Системный подход к изучению языка СМИ: Современная английская медиаречь / Т. Г. Добросклонская. – Москва: Флинта: Наука, 2008. – 263 с.
2. Nation M. A Dictionary of Modern Britain. London, 1991, p.6
3. Crystal David. The scope of Internet Linguistics. Paper presented at the American Association for the advancement of science meeting on 2011-07-26.
4. Hudson, R. A, 1996, Sociolinguistics, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press
5. Spolsky, B., 2010, Sociolinguistics, Oxford: Oxford University Press
6. Online Cambridge Dictionary: <http://dictionary.cambridge.org>
7. Online Oxford Learner’s Dictionary: <http://www.oxfordlearnersdictionaries.com/>
8. Online Reference Dictionary: <http://dictionary.reference.com>

9. Oxford dictionary [Электронный ресурс]. – Режим доступа:
<https://en.oxforddictionaries.com> (дата обращения: 25.07.2018)